

STAKEHOLDERS

- Water companies
- Local authorities
- Environment Agency & Natural England
- Abstractors
- River interest groups

CHALLENGES

- **Water quality** highly variable, with an impact on treatment costs
- Catchment **Partnerships** not collated at regional scale

AMBITION

- Pull **together different scales of partnerships** to deliver Integrated Catchment Management
- Highlight the **value of** collating public, private and community **data**
- Develop/improve a **smartphone app** for households to create awareness raising, water saving behaviors

INN WATER PARTNERS

A **consortium** gathering 13 organisations (Research and Technology Organisations, SMEs, end users, associations with EU and international coverages).

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INN WATER

Promoting
social innovation
to renew
multi-level and cross-sector
water governance

Pilot Site #4
WEST COUNTRY
United Kingdom

Led by

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WEST COUNTRY

The West Country Water Resources area covers the Western Peninsula of the United Kingdom from Bristol and Wiltshire down to Devon and Cornwall an area 23 000 km² with a population of 4,7 m people.

METHOD

1. Set the composition of pilot site community
2. Assess the current water governance situation
3. Set objectives and planning
4. Test and implement schemes and tools
5. Feedback and assessment

5 PILOT SITES

Implementing different types of governance mechanisms and covering different **water challenges**, test and co-develop the tools and methods.

INN WATER
Pilot Site Community

France, Réunion Island - **Economic focus**

Italy, Middle Brenta Basin - **Ecosystem services & Drinking water sector**

Spain, Figueres - **Water scarcity**

United Kingdom, West Country - **Water quality**

Hungary, Middle Tisza - **Water allocation**

